

Scaling Law for Entropy from MaxEnt Principle

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In (1), a scaling law: $d/dp (p h(p)) = b h(p/a)$ ((1)) is presented where a and b are constants and p is probability and $\sum_i p(i)h(p(i))$, entropy. This law is applied to a variety of distributions including the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis, Kaniadakis and Abe ones. It is argued in (1), that this law follows from the maximization of entropy $p h(p)$ using the constraints $\sum_i p(i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$.

We argue here that the scaling law follows naturally for power law distributions which involve a single power q or powers q and $-q$ as well as for the \ln function. We also note that the Tsallis form of MaxEnt does not use $p h(p)$ as entropy nor does it use $\sum_i e_i p(i)$ as a constraint, something that is inherent in the MaxEnt approach of (1) used to obtain ((1)).

Scaling Law

In (1), the useful scaling law for \ln and various single parameter power distributions (Tsallis, Kaniadakis, Abe etc) is presented, namely:

$$d/dp (p h(p)) = b h(p/a) \quad ((1))$$

It is argued in (1) that ((1)) follows from maximizing entropy, $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$ subject to the constraints $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i p(i) = 1$.

In particular:

$$d/dp \sum_i p(i) h(p(i)) = -1/T(e_i - u) \quad ((2))$$

Then: $p(i) = a \text{ hinverse} (-1/(bT) (e_i - u))$ ((3)) from which (1) argues that:

$$d/dp p(i) h(p(i)) = b h(p(i)/a) \quad ((3))$$

We try to argue that ((3)) follows naturally from the properties of single parameter power laws q , power laws with q and $-q$ and the \ln function.

Scaling Law Linked to Various Math Functions

We first consider the math function $\ln(p)$. Then:

$$d/dp (p \ln(p)) = 1 + \ln(p) = \ln(pe) \text{ so } ((1) \text{ is automatically satisfied with } b=1 \text{ and } a=1/e. \quad ((4))$$

Next, we consider a single power representing $h(p)$ i.e.

$$h(p) = a_1 + b_1 p^q \quad ((5))$$

The LHS side of ((1)) yields: $(a_1 + (b_1 + b_1 q) p^q)$ ((6))

Then $b=1$ and $a = (b_1/(b_1 + b_1 q))^{1/q}$ ((7)). This is the Tsallis case if $q \rightarrow 1-q$.

Finally, we consider the case of: $h(p) = a_1 p^q + a_2 p^{-q}$ ((7))

Then: $d/dp (p h(p)) = a_1(q+1) p^q + a_2(-q+1) p^{-q}$ ((8))

For ((1)) to hold: $(q+1) = b/(a p^q)$ and $(-q+1) = b/(a p^{-q})$

Thus: $(1-qq) = bb$ and $(q+1)/(q-1) = 1/(a p^{2q}) \rightarrow a = [(q-1)/(q+1)]^{1/(2q)}$ ((9))

((9)) is linked to the Abe and Kaniadakis distributions. Thus, we argue that there is no reason to introduce a maximization of entropy approach subject to constraints to obtain the scaling law ((1)).

Furthermore, we note that the MaxEnt approach ((2)) does not match the Tsallis case. The Tsallis entropy is:

Sum over i $p^q h(p)$ and the constraints are Sum over i $p(i)=1$ and Sum over i $e_i p^q = F$.

These are very different from what is used in ((2)). Thus, we suggest considering the scaling law ((1)) as representing math properties of ln and power law functions with single parameter powers q or q and $-q$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) presents a very useful scaling law ((1)), but argues that it follows from maximizing entropy Sum over i $p(i) h(p(i))$ subject to the constraints Sum over i $p(i)=1$ and Sum over i $e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$. This scaling law is then applied to various distributions including the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis, Abe and Kaniadakis ones. We note that in the Tsallis case, entropy is Sum over i $p(i)^q h(p(i))$ and the constraints are Sum over i $p(i)=1$ and Sum over i $p(i)^q e_i$. Thus, even though the scaling law still applies to the Tsallis case, the maximization of entropy subject to Sum over i $e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ and Sum over i $p(i)=1$ do not.

Instead we argue that the scaling law ((1)) follows from math properties of the ln and power laws involving a single parameter q or q and $-q$.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. and Scarfone, L. Deformed Logarithms and Entropies (2004)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0402418>